

A Valorous and Religious Woman: Bibi Balbir Kaur

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Abstract

The aim of the Gurdwara Reform Movement was to free the Gurdwaras from the clutches of the *Mahants*. In Sikh history, the Jaito Morcha was one of the peaceful Morchas of the Gurdwara Reform Movement. In these peaceful Morchas, both men and women who took bullets with open foreheads, to achieve peaceful martyrdom and protect religion, have contributed. The share of women in these Morchas was not less. Women also expressed the same sense of courage and bravery as men. After the first stage of the Jatha, when it became clear that women were not needed to prepare langar, the leader of the Jatha asked the women to go back. The other women agreed to go back after the leader of the Jatha asked them to, but Bibi Balbir Kaur did not wish to go back. She wanted to go with the Jatha. When the Jathedar asked her to go back, she said, "Don't stop me from participating in this fight, I am not afraid of death. I request that I be allowed to go with my brothers." The Jathedar, understanding her feelings of sacrificing her life, reluctantly agreed. Bibi Balbir Kaur demonstrated courage in this Morcha, having feelings of devotion and respect for religion. She sacrificed her life along with her child for her religion and sect. It was because of the sacrifices and martyrdom that the British government of that time had to bow down and was forced to enact the Gurdwara Act. With the passage of the Act, the historical Gurdwaras came under the management of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee.

Keywords Bibi Balbir Kaur, Gurdwara Reform Movement, Akali Movement, Jaito Morcha, Shaheedi Jatha, Gurdwara Act, Martial Law.

Introduction

The Akali movement holds special significance among the popular movements of the 20th century during the British rule. Initially, the main objective of the Akalis was to free the Gurdwaras from the clutches of the *Mahants*. This movement continued for several years. The sacrifices of the Sikhs in the Gurdwara Reform Movement created both enthusiasm and political awakening in the Sikh world. Hundreds of Sikhs were martyred and thousands were imprisoned in the Nankana Sahib massacre, Chabiyaan da Morcha, Guru ka Bagh and Jaito Morcha. In these peaceful morchas, the Indian National Congress supported the Akalis and among the Congress leaders, Mahatma Gandhi, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru etc., supported the Akalis. Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru was even imprisoned in the Jaito Morcha. In Sikh history, the Jaito Morcha was one of the peaceful Morchas of the Gurdwara Reform Movement which lasted longer than all the Sikh Morchas. The major achievement of this Morcha was that the British government was forced to enact the Gurdwara Act and finally the government had to bow down to the people's power. The Gurdwara Act was passed in 1925 AD, which led to the victory of the people's power. With the passing of the Gurdwara Act, all the historical Gurdwaras came under the management of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee.

Reasons for the Morcha

Jaito belonged to the Nabha princely state, which is located on the Bathinda to Ferozepur railway line.¹ Maharaja Ripudaman Singh of Nabha princely state was a freethinker and sympathized with the Akali movement. He had secretly supported the Akalis during the 'Guru Ka Bagh Morcha'. Such sympathy of the Maharaja towards the Akalis irritated the British government. Therefore, the British government was looking for any opportunity to remove the Maharaja. When the Maharaja of Nabha princely state had a quarrel with the Maharaja of Patiala, the government got an opportunity to take action against the

Maharaja. The government formed a committee under the chairmanship of John Stuart to investigate the quarrel. The committee found Maharaja Ripudaman Singh guilty and the government, accepting the decision of the committee, pressured the Maharaja to abdicate. Maharaja Ripudaman Singh was sent to Dehradun on 9 July 1923. A British officer was then appointed as the administrator of Nabha.² In other words, Maharaja Ripudaman Singh was deposed on 9 July 1923. This marked the beginning of the Jaito Morcha. The reasons for deposing the Maharaja of Nabha were political. The dispute between Maharaja Nabha and Patiala was merely an excuse. But the real reason was that Maharaja Ripudaman Singh was a free-thinking patriotic ruler unlike Maharaja Patiala, who was favored by the British Government. Since the beginning of the Akali movement, he supported the Akali Dal and gave free rein to the Sikhs in his state to work for the Gurdwara Reform Movement. During the arrests of the Akalis, he ignored government orders and did not arrest the Akalis. After the Nankana Sahib massacre, Nabha was the only Sikh state where Sikhs celebrated the martyrdom day of the martyrs of Nankana Sahib and could freely roam wearing kirpans and black turbans. Numerous allegations were leveled against Maharaja Nabha by Maharaja Patiala. The British government sent Mr. Stuart to Ambala on the pretext of investigating the Nabha-Patiala dispute. Stuart decided against Maharaja Nabha. This led the British government to force Maharaja Nabha to abdicate. This decision promoted the Akalis to launch a movement against the British government. On September 1, 1923, the Shiromani Akali Dal sent a Jatha towards Jaito.³

Objective of study

1. To present the courage and heroic martyrdom of Bibi Balbir Kaur.
2. To describe the spirit of sacrifice of Sikh women towards religion and community.
3. To highlight the participation of Sikh women in the Gurdwara Reform Movement.

Review of Literature

Some authors have written about Bibi Balbir Kaur in their books, which gives information about her courage and devotion to religion. No purely historical comparative study has been done on Bibi Balbir Kaur.

1. Grewal, Dalwinder Singh (2015), *Sikh Shaheedi Lehran*, Part-2 (in Punjabi), Dharam Prachar Committee, Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, Sri Amritsar
2. Dilgeer, Harjinder Singh (tr. by Ibben Kalan, Amarjit Kaur) (2015), *100 Sikh Bibian* (in Punjabi), Sikh University Press, Amritsar
3. Chandan, Kirpal Singh (editor) (2017), *Itihasik Sikh Bibian* (in Punjabi), Sikh Missionary College, Ludhiana

In this research paper, a purely historical comparative study has been done on Bibi Balbir Kaur. This research paper will be a unique historical research paper on Bibi Balbir Kaur at the academic level.

Main Text

At this time, the administration of the state was handed over to a British administrator, Wilson Johnston, by the British government who strictly prohibited any resolution, discussions or *Path* regarding Maharaja Ripudaman Singh. A kind of martial law was imposed in the state due to which processions and meetings were stopped in the state. Even mentioning the restoration of Nabha in the *Ardas* was deemed a major crime, let alone giving speeches about it. For a few days, Jathas of 25 Akalis continued their march, but the state authorities captured them and exiled them far from the region. On September 11, a Jatha of 110 *Singhs* reached Jaito via Muktsar while vowing to maintain peaceful. They got the *Akhand Path Parkash* inaugurated in Gurdwara Gangsar Sahib. However, the imprisonment of the *Singhs* in the presence of Sri Guru Granth Sahib, gave the movement a religious undertone, sparking anger among the common Sikh people. At this time, a decision was taken to complete the *Akhand Path Sahib* in its entirety. Subsequently, Jathas of 25 *Singhs* began marching to Jaito daily from Akal Takht Sahib. The Jathas were appealed to remain calm in all situations and were strictly prohibited from taking any retaliatory action. Members of the Jatha were arrested held for two or three days, beaten, starved and then transported in vehicles to Nabha *Bir* or further to Rewari before being released. Determined *Singhs* walk 300 miles to reach Sri Amritsar and join the next Jathas. The Indian National Congress also showed interest in this Morcha. Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru, Mr. Santanam and Principal Gidwani were sent to get complete information about the Morcha. Later they were imprisoned in Nabha Jail. Later, he was tried and sentenced to two and a half years in prison, but this imprisonment was soon suspended. He was taken to Nabha station and released. The organizations that ran the Jaito Morcha, the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee and the Akali Dal, were declared illegal and all the leaders were subsequently arrested. They were charged with serious crimes and sentenced to long imprisonment, black water and even hanging.⁴ In other words, the growing courage of the Akalis and the Jaito Morcha created panic among the government officials. They wanted to take strong steps to stop the Akalis. Therefore, the government declared the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, the Akali Dal and other Sikh organizations illegal on 12 October 1923. All the members of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee were arrested. Due to great enthusiasm

among the Akalis, they started doing the work of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee secretly and kept sending their Jathas to Jaito.⁵

The Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee and the Akali Dal decided to send 500-500 Shaheedi Jathas to resume and complete the interrupted *Akhand Path Sahib* at Gangsar Jaito and to open the pilgrimage to the Gurdwara. The first Shaheedi Jatha was sent from Akal Takht Sahib on 9 February 1924 AD, consisting of Akali and Nirmale Singhs. The Jatha was asked to remain calm and do its work.⁶ Sardar Udham Singh Nagoke was appointed as the Jathedar of this Jatha, but he was arrested before the Jatha could leave. Therefore, Sardar Udham Singh Varpal was appointed as the Jathedar in his place.⁷

Women were not allowed to go with the Jatha. But they insisted on participating in this work. They managed to go with the Jatha with the idea of preparing langar for the Jatha on the way. Bibi Balbir Kaur was leading the women along with her two-year-old child. When the Jatha stopped for the first stage, the people of the area served the Jatha a lot. Therefore, after the first stage, it became clear that women were not needed to prepare langar. Therefore, the leader of the Jatha asked the women to go back. The other women agreed to go back, but Bibi Balbir Kaur did not want to go back. She wanted to go with the Jatha. When the Jathedar asked her to go back, she said, "Do not stop me from participating in this fight, I am not afraid of death. I request that I be allowed to go with my brothers." The Jathedar, understanding her feelings of sacrificing her life, reluctantly agreed. Keeping the objective in mind, the members of the Jatha moved forward under the leadership of the Jathedar. Everyone was ready to sacrifice their lives in every way. On the way, people served the Jatha with milk, sweets, etc. and showered flowers. The last stage of the Jatha was on 20 February 1924 AD. was in the village of Bargari in the state of Faridkot. From here on 21 February 1924 AD, after the morning Diwan, the Jatha was to leave for Jaito. When the Jatha was going in lines of four, a 22 years old young woman, Bibi Balbir Kaur, was walking with the Jatha. She looked like a goddess of purity and sacrifice. Her two-year-old child was the center of attraction. When the Jatha reached near its destination, the Jathedar said that the British soldiers are ready to kill us with their machine guns. I request everyone that only those who have received permission from the Akal Takht Sahib should go forward and the rest should go back. Some went back and some found another way. But Bibi Balbir Kaur did not choose any other way along with her son and continued walking with the rest of the Jatha. When the Jathedar came to know about it, he came to Bibi Balbir Kaur and said, sister, there is a danger of being shot ahead, do not go forward. At this time, Balbir Kaur folded her hands and said, do not stop me, I am also an *Amritdhari Singhni* and have taken a vow to serve the sect. If I too become a martyr with my 500 brothers, I will consider myself fortunate. The Gurus have given equal status to women. Stopping me from going forward would be discrimination. If you are worried about my child, let him serve the sect, he cannot get a better opportunity than this. After this, Bibi Balbir Kaur hugged the child and could not say anything else because she was emotional. The Jathedar and the members of the Jatha tried hard to convince Balbir Kaur to go back, but Bibi Balbir Kaur remained adamant to embrace death with her brothers. Because of this, the Jathedar also agreed to accept Balbir Kaur's decision.⁸

The rulers had made complete preparations to fire on the Jatha. Machine guns were mounted on the fort and a large number of soldiers and armed police were present. The government had planned to surround the Jatha with barbed wire and kill it with bullets. Bibi Kishan Kaur and Bibi Tej Kaur had witnessed all this arrangement in disguise and these women had told the Jatha the whole truth.⁹ When the Jatha was about 150 yards behind Gurdwara Tibbi Sahib, a European officer stopped the Jatha from moving forward and said that if you move forward, you will be shot. Despite this warning, the Jatha did not stop and kept moving forward. At the signal of the administrator, bullets started being fired on the Jatha from three sides. The bullets continued for five minutes but the Jatha moved forward peacefully and courageously. No one turned back. Many fell and then got up with courage and moved forward and many were martyred on this occasion. At this time, Bibi Balbir Kaur was moving forward carrying her son. Suddenly, a bullet hit Balbir Kaur on the forehead. Her face was stained with blood. But she did not stop and kept moving forward. Her child kept wiping the blood from her face. Then a bullet hit the child in her arms and the child died. Balbir Kaur kissed the child's forehead and placed his dead body next to the other injured and dead and ran to join the members of the Jatha moving forward. Balbir Kaur's face had turned pale due to excessive bleeding and her legs were wobbling, but still she kept moving forward with the members of the Jatha. After reaching near Gurdwara Tibbi Sahib, she thanked God. The firing had not stopped yet. Suddenly, a bullet hit her chest and Balbir Kaur fell to the ground and died. Even at that time, her blood-stained face was filled with enthusiasm.¹⁰ Bibi Balbir Kaur made an unparalleled sacrifice forever. The community whose women sacrifice their lives with laughter and sacrifice their lives for the sake of the nation and make a piece of milk-

sucking liver martyred in Morcha of their eyes and say that we have completed a task on our own. That community can never go to the bottom of the valley.¹¹

This martyrdom is very high in the eyes of the Sikhs because the Jatha did not suddenly become a victim of bloodshed. From the very beginning, the Jatha was sure that they had to make a priceless sacrifice for religion. Knowing everything, the Jatha went to see the game of their destiny with a cheerful face and the Sikhs were martyred while enduring bullets on their chests. They endured hardships but did not care even a bit about the British rule in their efforts to gain the freedom of religious rights to go to the Gurdwara and recite. After the firing in the first Shaheed Jatha, a wave of enthusiasm and excitement spread in the Sikh sect. There was talk of the Jaito Morcha in every home. When the Diwans were decorated in the Gurdwaras, the sacrifices of the martyrs of Jaito were narrated. Every Sikh's heart wanted to go to Jaito and gain fame by attaining martyrdom. Small children used to sing in the streets that "*Aji main nabha nu jaroor javaga bhave sir kat jave mera.*" The unparalleled sacrifices of the martyrs of Jaito breathed new life into the Sikh sect. The incident of firing in Jaito created panic in the entire country. All the Sabha societies started expressing sympathy with the Akalis and there was strong opposition to the government's oppression. A resolution was passed in the meeting of the All India Working Committee under the chairmanship of Maulana Muhammad Ali, expressing sympathy with the Sikh community and assuring all kinds of help. Mahatma Gandhi also expressed his sorrow over this incident and the President of the Khilafat Committee, Shaukat Ali, also expressed his sympathy with the Sikhs. A rally was held by the citizens of Calcutta to express sympathy with the Sikh community. In which various leaders presented the real situation of Jaito before the people and at the end a resolution was passed which said that "This joint rally of Hindus, Muslims and Sikhs of Calcutta strongly condemns and expresses protest against the firing by the government on the peaceful Singhs who were going to perform Akhand Path in Gurdwara Gangsar Jaito and congratulates the Akalis who achieved peaceful martyrdom for having bravely taken bullets to protect their religion".¹²

The role of women in the Gurdwara reform movement was not small because it was uncommon for women to tie death twine with their own hands while sending their sons, husbands and brothers away from home.¹³ Many women who were serving the wounded in the Jaito Morcha were brutally beaten and arrested. In addition, a woman who was serving the wounded was abused by the soldiers and ordered to leave the place, but when she refused, the soldiers pushed her badly from the 20-foot height of Tibbi Sahib. Similarly, a British officer severely whipped a Sikh woman who had refused to obey the British officer's order.¹⁴

Methodology

To complete the paper, sources were reviewed according to the historical research method; an effort has been made to write on the basis of historical facts and comparative analysis has also been used to complete the research paper. The paper has been written using the research method from a historical perspective.

Conclusion

Bibi Balbir Kaur demonstrated her courage in the Jaito Morcha while maintaining her devotion and respect for her religion. She did not hesitate to sacrifice her life as well as the life of her child for her religion and sect. The sacrifice of everyone during the Jaito Morcha was unparalleled, but 22 years old Bibi Balbir Kaur, due to her courage, fortitude and bravery, filled the Sikhs with a new spirit and enthusiasm. Bibi Balbir Kaur's bravery and martyrdom hold a unique status in history. Such a brave example will always remain inspiring for the coming generations of the community and Bibi Balbir Kaur's name will always shine in the pages of history. The Jaito Morcha continued even after this and Jathas continued to go and the Jathas continued to gain strength from the martyrdoms.

References

1. Nabha, Kahn Singh (2011), *Mahan Kosh, Encyclopaedia of Sikh Literature (in Punjabi)*, Language Department Punjab, Jalandhar, p. 533
2. Arora, A.C. (editor) (1989), *Punjab Dian Lok Lehan 1849-1947 (in Punjabi)*, Publication Bureau, Punjabi University, Patiala, pp. 140-141
3. Arora, A.C. (editor) (1989), *Punjab Dian Lok Lehan 1849-1947 (in Punjabi)*, Publication Bureau, Punjabi University, Patiala, pp. 208-209; Maharaja Ripudaman Singh had pro-Akali sympathies and fully supported the Guru Ka Bagh Morcha. He wore a black turban as a protest against the massacre at Nankana Sahib - Harbans Singh (2016), *Encyclopedia of Sikhism, Part II*, Punjabi University, Patiala, p. 327; There were several Jathas in the Akali Dal and any Sikh who wanted to participate in the Gurdwara Reform Movement could become a member of a Jatha. Most of the members of these Jathas were small farmers from the villages - Home Department (Political), File No. 459/11/1922
4. Grewal, Dalwinder Singh (2015), *Sikh Shaheedi Lehan, Part-2 (in Punjabi)*, Dharam Prachar Committee, Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, Sri Amritsar, pp. 103-104; Arora, A.C. (editor) (1989), *Punjab Dian Lok Lehan 1849-1947 (in Punjabi)*, Publication Bureau, Punjabi University, Patiala, pp. 208-209; This Akali Morcha had the full support of the Congress. The Congress sent three of

- its members, including Jawaharlal Nehru, to the Jaito Morcha. But they were arrested in advance by the British officers and were not allowed to go to the Morcha - Arora, A.C. (editor) (1989), *Punjab Dian Lok Lehran 1849-1947 (in Punjabi)*, Publication Bureau, Punjabi University, Patiala, p. 141; The members of the Jatha were prevented from entering Nabha state and were detained and beaten by the police. After this, they were left in the remote desert without food or water - Harbans Singh (2016), *Encyclopedia of Sikhism, Part II*, Punjabi University, Patiala, p. 328; The Congress sent three of its members to the Jaito Morcha, including Jawaharlal Nehru. But they were arrested in advance by the British officers and were not allowed to go to the Morcha - Jawaharlal Nehru *An Autobiography* (1982), Jawaharlal Nehru Memorial Fund, New Delhi, p. 110
5. Arora, A.C. (editor) (1989), *Punjab Dian Lok Lehran 1849-1947 (in Punjabi)*, Publication Bureau, Punjabi University, Patiala, p. 141; Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee and Akali Dal were declared illegal on 13 October 1924 AD - Grewal, Dalwinder Singh (2015), *Sikh Shaheedi Lehran, Part-2 (in Punjabi)*, Dharam Prachar Committee, Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, Sri Amritsar, p. 103; The government declared Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, Akali Dal and other Sikh organizations illegal on 12 October 1923 AD and all the members of Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee were arrested - Nabha Records, File No. 28, Punjab State Archives, Patiala.
 6. Grewal, Dalwinder Singh (2015), *Sikh Shaheedi Lehran, Part-2 (in Punjabi)*, Dharam Prachar Committee, Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, Sri Amritsar, p. 105; Sikhs had set examples of enduring suffering peacefully in Guru Ka Bagh. But seeing the Jatha of 500 leaving, doubts arose in the minds of the people that these brave persons would be able to fulfill their vow of remaining peaceful? At that time, Congress leader Mahatma Gandhi had expressed doubts that the march of 500 Sikhs in a uniform with a band playing music towards the Gurdwara was not a peaceful demonstration but rather an attempt to impose their military power on the government. But when the Jatha reached Jaito and many Sikhs sacrificed their lives peacefully, the eyes of the doubting leaders and the people were opened - Visakha Singh (1998), *Sikh History of Maalwa, Part III (in Punjabi)*, Chatar Singh Jeevan Singh, Amritsar, p. 621
 7. Grewal, Dalwinder Singh (2015), *Sikh Shaheedi Lehran, Part-2 (in Punjabi)*, Dharam Prachar Committee, Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, Sri Amritsar, p. 105
 8. Chandan, Kirpal Singh (editor) (2017), *Itihasik Sikh Bibian (in Punjabi)*, Sikh Missionary College, Ludhiana, pp. 106-107; No information is available about Bibi Balbir Kaur's early life.
 9. Visakha Singh (1998), *Sikh History of Maalwa, Part III (in Punjabi)*, Chatar Singh Jeevan Singh, Amritsar, p. 626
 10. Chandan, Kirpal Singh (editor) (2017), *Itihasik Sikh Bibian (in Punjabi)*, Sikh Missionary College, Ludhiana, pp. 106-108; When the police fired, one bullet hit the child and the child died. Balbir Kaur put the child on one side of the road and herself continued to move forward with the Jatha - Dilgeer, Harjinder Singh (tr. by Ibben Kalan, Amarjit Kaur) (2015), *100 Sikh Bibian (in Punjabi)*, Sikh University Press, Amritsar, p. 96; A mother's abandoned child was shot. Due to which the innocent child started climbing as soon as he was shot. The mother put the child on the ground and herself continued to move forward with the Jatha - Visakha Singh (1998), *Sikh History of Maalwa, Part III (in Punjabi)*, Chatar Singh Jeevan Singh, Amritsar, p. 626
 11. Visakha Singh (1998), *Sikh History of Maalwa, Part I (in Punjabi)*, Chatar Singh Jeevan Singh, Amritsar, p. 539
 12. Visakha Singh (1998), *Sikh History of Maalwa, Part III (in Punjabi)*, Chatar Singh Jeevan Singh, Amritsar, pp. 630-639
 13. Acharwal, Jarnail Singh (2014), *Bharat di Azadi vich Punjab da Hissa (in Punjabi)*, National Book Trust, India, New Delhi, p. 115
 14. Visakha Singh (1998), *Sikh History of Maalwa, Part III (in Punjabi)*, Chatar Singh Jeevan Singh, Amritsar, pp. 627-628